

NEWSLETTER

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“ One of the pillars of the DECIDO project is the introduction of co-creation in evidence-based policy making. ”

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DECIDO MAPPING OF STAKEHOLDERS

There are various definitions of co-creation but all of them involve the participation of public and private actors in the design, management, delivery and evaluation of public services. DECIDO's methodological approach, including co-creation, is being tested in 4 pilots in the disaster risk management domain. A key component of the co-creation process is the identification of the public and private actors that should be involved in each phase of the process. This identification in DECIDO has been carried out taking into account the characteristics of its four pilots:

- 1) Finnish pilot on forest fires in the City of Kajaani.
 - 2) Italian pilot on floods, on response to the COVID19 pandemic and on psychological protection of youth in Torino.
 - 3) Greek pilot on power outage in Greek municipalities.
 - 4) Spanish pilot on fires in the Aragon region.
- Following the collection of information from these four pilots DECIDO has identified four types of sta-

keholders:

- Social actors: includes the group or community that are passive subjects of emergency situations, civil society organisations, religious associations, media, traders, entrepreneurs and, in particular, citizens.
- Intervention actors: includes all those involved in direct intervention in emergency situations such as the rescue service, fire service, emergency medical services, police, civil protection authorities, volunteers,
- Providers of information, knowledge, expertise and consultancy. This is a heterogeneous group of stakeholders who can contribute ideas, suggestions and solutions to complement and improve the emergency protocols in place.
- Political actors, who do not intervene directly in emergency situations but are responsible for making decisions affecting emergency response protocols, mainly policy makers.

The detailed breakdown of stakeholders in each pilot is shown below:

Finnish pilot:

There is only one social actor, the Social and healthcare service department of the City of Kajaani (SOTE)

The intervention actors are the Regional firefighting and rescue services in Kainuu (KAIPE) and the Kainuu regional police force.

There are several information, advice, knowledge and expertise providers such as the YLE news channel, Social media channels, the 112 app, providers of data on weather (Ilmatieteenlaitos), terrain (Maanmittauslaitos), statistics (Tilastokeskus), maps (Kajaani Info GIS) and traffic (Traficom), and the emergency reporting system PRONTO.

The political actor is the Department Directors Board of the City of Kajaani.

Italian pilot:

Social actors such as the Social services branch of the Municipality of Turin, the Volunteer Support Centre of Torino (Vol.To) and the Local Council for people in difficulties (CPD).

The intervention actor is the Civil protection office of the Municipality of Turin.

The information provider actor is the Regional Environmental Protection Agency of Piedmont (ARPA).

The political actors are the Councillors for Social Policies and the Councillors for Civil Protection both at local level (Municipality of Turin) and regional level (Piedmont Region).

Greek pilot:

The social actor is the Social Services of the Municipality of Halki.

There are several intervention actors such as the Civil Protection of the Municipality of Halki, the Regional police force, the Regional fire department of Halki, the Regional medical clinic and the Port Authority of Halki.

Information providers are the social media channels.

The political actor is the Municipality of Halki and more specifically municipal council members dealing with civil protection issues.

Spanish pilot:

Social actors are the Aragonese Federation of Municipalities and Regions (FAMP) and the Regions and municipalities of Aragón.

There are several intervention actors such as Civil Protection of the Government of Aragón, the Aragonese Agro-Environmental Management Society (SARGA), Nature protecting agents (APN Aragón), the Military Emergency Unit (UME) and the General Direction of Natural Environment and Forest Management of the Government of Aragón.

There are two information, advice, knowledge and expertise providers such as the Meteorology Statal Agency (AEMET) and the Aragon Fire Operational Information (INFOAR).

The political actor (also with intervention responsibilities) is the General Direction of Natural Environment and Forest Management of the Government of Aragón.

All types of stakeholders can contribute to the four phases of the policy life cycle identified in DECIDO, but it is the responsibility of each pilot, depending on the challenges it wants to address, to determine which stakeholders should be involved in each phase:

Photo by Jacel Dylag on Unsplash

THE HACKATHON OF THE ARAGON PILOT

The first hackathon of the Aragon pilot took place on 5 May 2022. In order to prepare for the hackathon, several meetings were held with the Directorate General for the Natural Environment and Forest Management, as well as with TECNALIA and SARGA. In these previous meetings, it was suggested that the Aragon pilot be oriented towards the resolution of a problem associated with each of the fires that occur in this autonomous community: that of establishing the necessary mechanisms for the correct management of alert situations due to the smoke associated with wildfire. Correct management in this area will make possible, among other things, to foresee the measures and equipment for the evacuation of the population from an area where a certain risk of smoke inhalation associated with a fire is foreseen, and also to minimise the risk to which fire-fighting patrols may be exposed during the performance of their duties. In these preliminary meetings, the need for a smoke trajectory simulation tool was also identified.

After this first series of meetings, advice was sought from researchers at the University of Zaragoza who are experts in dispersion modelling. Specifically, several meetings were held with the researcher Adrian Navas, from the University of Zaragoza. In these meetings we explored the various models and tools available, such as FALL3D, used by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), HYSPLIT, used by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and FLEXPART, from the University of Vienna. We

chose the latter mainly because of the availability of the code and its ability to work with various meteorological models, such as the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Integrated Forecast System (IFS) and data from the United States National Centers of Environmental Prediction (NCEP) Global Forecast System (GFS).

But having a correct forecast does not ensure that evacuation plans and policies are in place to minimise the risk to firefighting resources. Therefore, on 5 May 2022, a first hackathon was held at the Ibercivis-University of Zaragoza facilities to 1) explain the project to the attendees, 2) explore various processes of citizen participation in similar projects already carried out in Aragon thanks to the Aragon Open Government Laboratory (LAAAB), 3) explore the FLEXPART tool and discuss who would be the agents responsible for establishing the relevant policies in case of smoke alert and see, in what form and by what means it would be appropriate to warn the public.

The hackathon on 5 May was attended by actors from various fields. In addition to members of the consortium (Ibercivis, Sarga, Tecnalía), representatives of the Government of Aragon, members of academia (specifically, the Department of Geography of the University of Zaragoza) and citizens (members of the mapping association Geoinquietos) attended the hackathon.

Beyond the presentation of the project by Francisco Sanz (Ibercivis) and Xabier Uriarte (Tecnalia), Susana Barriga (LAAAB) spoke about citizen participation, and the importance of having a very diverse conversation, with different professional profiles, origins, socio-economic levels, since it is in this variety of participants that collective intelligence emerges. What LAAAB does is to help those who are in charge of managing the participatory process, providing a methodology, accompaniment in the process and the reporting of the project. Barriga also focused his intervention on how LAAAB works and how they disseminate the processes of citizen participation to reach as many actors as possible.

The session also served to get to know the FLEXPART tool. Simulations of the execution of this tool were carried out, which allowed us to know the structure of the input and output files and therefore to face the next steps of the implementation of the tool in this pilot.

The last part of the session was devoted to discuss the implications resulting from the forecasts made by FLEXPART. Some of the questions that were debated were: Who should decide on the evacuation policies of the public? Who should be able to run simulations in a risk situation? How should the evacuation of a population be communicated to the public if necessary?

Some of the conclusions reached after the co-creation session:

- It is necessary and an opportunity to establish a collaboration between LAAAB (because of its capacity to map essential actors) and DECIDO.
- It is necessary also to establish effective collaborations between the University of Zaragoza and DECIDO. The comments and ideas that the University of Zaragoza can contribute to DECIDO's services can be very valuable.
- It is essential to work together with citizen science associations (such as Geoinquietos) as they can collaborate in the process of mapping critical points or infrastructures, etc.
- It is necessary to incorporate other departments of the Government of Aragon into the project when necessary (e.g. 112, which is in charge of managing emergency situations

Photo by Mikhail Fesenko on Unsplash

DECIDO PRIVACY AND ETHICS MANAGEMENT

The starting point of the Ethics Review in the DECIDO project is the evaluation of the situation ex ante the pilot phase describing for each of the four pilots the framework of data privacy condition.

The strong proposition is, of course, that where a type of data processing is likely to result in a high risk for the rights and freedoms of individuals, controllers shall carry out a Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) prior to the processing to assess the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data.

The DPIA (of Privacy Impact Assessment, PIA) is an important tool for any organisation's accountability. Conducting a PIA is a highly recommended good practice, and even mandatory in some cases, as it helps organisations build data processing privacy-friendly and be compliant with the GDPR. DECIDO project, after a preliminary

exercise based on the guidelines developed by the GDPR.eu decided, due to the increased complexity to use for the next steps (the deliverable foreseen at month 27 named D5.1 ver2), to adopt a free PIA software to assist the controllers going through this process. This SW has been developed by the Commission Nationale de L'informatique et des Libertés CNIL the French DP Authority which focus on data coming from external contributors in term of co-creation practices identified and the strategic approaches to apply infrastructural and analytical power provided by the EU cloud in disaster risk management policy domains.

This user-friendly tool unfolds the PIA methodology CNIL has been developing since 2015. Following this methodology will allow organisations to be compliant with the requirements defined in the WP29 Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment adopted in October 2017. By releasing this tool now, CNIL gives data con-

trollers a chance to get familiar with this methodology and to be ready for May 2018.

The PIA software tool offers several features facilitating the PIA process

A contextual knowledge base based directly on the GDPR, the PIA guides and the Security guide published by CNIL. While conducting the analysis, the controller will be provided with a custom knowledge base;

Visualizations tools have been specially designed to ensure a quick understanding of the risks involved with the data processing at stake.

Currently in its beta version, the PIA software tool will be improved on the basis of feedbacks received from users. For that purpose, the tool is available under a free license: anyone can develop new features, answering your specific needs, and share them afterward with the community. CNIL will publish a finalized version in 2018, before the GDPR comes into effect.

The CNIL also plans to publish a framework for conducting DPIAs on connected objects and a case study by the end of the year.

Finally, to complete these tools, the next work will focus on the creation of two lists:

processings that require a DPIA;

processings that do not need to be subject to a DPIA.

The infographic in the previous page outlines the main principles.

Photo by Matthew Henry on Unsplash

THE FINNISH PILOT ON FOREST FIRES AND EVACUATION

Over the past six months, the Finnish pilot has been slowly taking shape. The incident actors have convened on multiple occasions to examine the needs and challenges they face in their work, and how it may affect future forest fires and evacuation procedures in the region.

The Kainuu Rescue Services, Social and Healthcare Services, departments of Kajaani City and civil organisations have met to learn from each other on procedures, resourcing, needs, and identified risks. During the period between May and September of 2022, the parties have held additional meetings in order to support interdepartmental communications, recognise joint strengths and weaknesses, and identify the next steps in addressing them. Led by the Kainuu Rescue Services (KAJ), the group will use the new knowledge paired with data gathered from incidents, internal operations, regional and national statistics, and work on formulating adequate policies to address the future needs of fires and evacuations in the region of Kainuu.

The leading questions of the working group were: 1) how to lessen the burden of firefighters during forest fires, 2) how to facilitate access to external equipment and expertise in the event of forest fires, and 3) how to facilitate the use of firefighting and rescue services in the Kainuu Rescue Department. The group identified that access and sharing of information is a key factor to cooperation across departments. The group postulates that improved access to relevant information will lead to better policy formulation for the involved parties and can lessen the burden of the engagement of firefighters.

By the end of June 2022, closed and open meetings were held to start planning deeper collaborations internally. At the same time, public events where evacuation centres were introduced to citizens across the regions aided in the dissemination, communication and engagement with citizens to gather insight into the proposed concepts, while addressing any concerns. Of particular interest to both parties is the significance of external equipment and expertise that is required during large scale incidents. When required, both citizens and business are needed to help in specific tasks in prevention of dama-

ges, provision of support to firefighters, and evacuation. A first indication of that is the requirement of a shared information bank on accessing such resources in times of emergency and ensuring that they can be utilized efficiently when required. Such implementation will require the analysis of prior incidents to establish a database of resourcing for various emergencies, ensuring that the information is up to date, and that services are utilized correctly. The group seeks to create a common policy for resource use in the region, optimizing workflows and cross-departmental communication.

Over the autumn period of 2022, the group will convene to start working on policy creation. An important factor in such joint policy design are the various duties, reports, needs, and existing risk analyses which the departments need to follow. The new policy drafts cannot interfere with existing tasks that may hinder the operations of any singular unit, requiring time to review and accept changes. To facilitate the collaboration further, the DECIDO portal will be utilized. Decisions, resources, documents, policies that exist will be used in the new policy creation process. Through the portal, the parties aim to utilize technologies share information and data, while working to co-create new policies for the region.

Figure 1. Old fire watch tower near the city of Kajaani.

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CONSORTIUM

